

Research Article (DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.15580/GJAS.2014.6.030714135>)

Factors Affecting Loan Repayment Performance among Members of Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society in Yewa North Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria

***Akerele E.O., Aihonsu J.O.Y., Ambali O.I. and Oshisanya K.P.**

Department of Agricultural Economics and Farm Management, College of Agricultural Sciences, Olabisi Onabanjo University, Yewa Campus, P.M.B 0012, Ayetoro Ogun State, Nigeria.

ARTICLE INFO

Article No.: 030714135

DOI: 10.15580/GJAS.2014.6.030714135

Submitted: 07/03/2014

Accepted: 11/06/2014

Published: 08/07/2014

***Corresponding Author**

Akerele E.O.

E-mail: akereleeze@gmail.com

Keywords:

Credit, Cooperative, Repayment, Loan, Income

ABSTRACT

The study focused on the investigation of factors affecting loan repayment performance among members of Cooperative Thrift and Credit Societies in Yewa North Local Government Area of Ogun State. The study drew a sample of hundred and four smallholder agricultural credit users who are members of Cooperative Thrift and credit society identified through a multi stage random sampling techniques. Relevant information on socio-economic characteristics, sources of loan preferred, payback period, factors affecting loan repayment of cooperators and constraints in obtaining loan were collected using structured questionnaires with personal interview and data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics and multiple regressions. The results of the study revealed that a total of 78.8 percent of the respondents was within the age range of 31-60 years showing that majority of the respondents are within their active and productive ages. The study also revealed that 89.5 percent of the respondents have formal education which facilitates their access to loans through informal sources and with Cooperative Thrift and Credit Societies being the most popular source, and credit was made available and utilized, and cooperators' annual income rose significantly. The results of the regression showed that amount of loan collected by farmers, level of education and year of experience and labor used were the major factors that positively and significantly influence loan repayment. It is therefore recommended that the credit agencies should always endeavour to draw a more convenient disbursement and amortization schedule to conform with economic needs, that is, loan must be adapted to the peculiar needs of the cooperators and repayment condition should be flexible enough to allow for variation and uncertainties in cooperative income.

INTRODUCTION

According to Momoh and Oso (1997), Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society is defined as “a financial self-help co-operative which encourages members to save money together and pooled resources and then used to provide low-cost loans to members.” They again stated that, “Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society operates within a clearly defined area of location and a mutual link must exist between all members. This link is known as the common bond of the Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society. The common bond may be based on all members living in the same locality or all members working for the same employer”. Berthoud and Hinton (1989) also defined Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society as being co-operative societies that offer loans to their members out of the pool of savings that are built up by the members themselves. This is a descriptive definition that does not refer to the purpose of Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society. However, it does describe them as being co-operatives; therefore co-operative principles could be inferred as being the purpose of Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society. The unique ownership status implicit in this definition (member run, owned and used) led to them being described by Croteau (1956) as being the purest form of co-operative. Not only are trading transactions restricted to members, restrictions are also placed on the membership by requiring that members belong to a common bond. This common bond or interest is usually multiple, associational, occupational or residential. The requirement to belong to a common bond is seen as a cornerstone in the success of these usually high-risk credit co-operatives, as the social pressure that is created by the members knowing each other, lessens the risk of default.

Again, World Council of Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society (WOCCU) defined Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society as non-bank financial institutions owned and controlled by members. It is also a democratic, member-owned financial co-operative. Each member, regardless of account size in the Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society, may run for the board and cast a vote in elections. As financial intermediaries, Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society finance their loan portfolios by mobilizing members' savings and shares rather than using outside capital, thus providing opportunities for generations of members. Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society exist to serve their members and communities. As not-for-profit cooperative institutions, Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society use excess earnings to offer members more affordable loans, a higher return on savings, lower fees or new products and services. They serve members from all walks of life, including the poor and disenfranchised (Ayanwale and Bamire, 2000). Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society provide members the opportunity to own their own financial institution and help them create opportunities such as starting small

businesses, building family homes and educating their children. In some countries, members encounter their first taste of democratic decision making through their Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society.

Cooperative Thrift and Credit Societies are safe, convenient places to access affordable financial services. Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society offer a full range of financial services, giving members greater flexibility to meet their individual needs. In some countries, Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society are known by different names to better express those services. In Afghanistan, for example, Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society are called Islamic Investment and Finance Cooperatives (IIFCs) to comply with Islamic lending practices. In Africa, they are known as Savings and Credit Co-operative Societies (SACCOs) to emphasize savings before credit. Acquisition of houses, cars, land, and payment of medical expenses, funeral expenses and rent advances are a few needs that members of a Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society expect to be satisfied with as and when they arise (Adeyemo, 1982; Openiyi, 1982; Onyenwaku and Ozoh, 1992). The aims of a Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society are multiple and a mixture of financial and social aims. The financial aims can be broadly summarized as to:

- Promote thrift by encouraging members to save regularly.
- Provide loans to members at a reasonable rate of interest.
- Assist members to make more effective use of their financial resources.

The current worldwide economic recession call for effective lending and excellent loan administration in order to increase the productivity of the peasant households. This will consequently affect the members of thrift and credit cooperative. Structurally, Nigeria's agriculture is in the hands of small- scale farmers, cultivating less than 5 hectares of land (Ijere, 1998; Osuntogun and Oludimu 1981). Studies on smallholder loan schemes revealed that the schemes are constrained by poor loan repayment (Simanowitz and Walter, 2002) and this has been attributed by many factors. It had been observed that most small- scale farmers do not possess the ability to repay back loans at the due time because of so many constraints which later has an adverse effect on the cooperative thrift and credit society. With this effect the society will not be able to meet the felt needs of their members. The need to prevent this drastic scenario in the society informs the objectives.

The main objective of the study is to assess factors affecting the loan repayment performance among members of cooperative thrift and credit society in Yewa North Local Government Area of Ogun State. The

specific objectives are to determine the loan repayment rates of cooperators; and examine the factors affecting loan procurement, utilization and repayment.

METHODOLOGY

The Study Area and Methods of Data Collection

This research study was carried out in Yewa North Local Government Area of Ogun State. Both primary and secondary data were used for the study. Primary data were collected through well-structured questionnaires which were used to collect information data on the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents and their loan performance activities. Secondary data were obtained from journals, textbooks, past project, bulletins, and newspapers.

Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

Simple random and purposive sampling procedures were adopted for the purpose of the study. In the study area, there are 8 cooperative multipurpose Unions out of which six are functioning and operating Thrift and Credit. From the six Unions, 50 percent were selected. These resulted into the selection of Ifedapo Ayetoro , Toluwalase and Ifeoluwa. The selected unions are made up of varying number of CTCS and CMS, as indicated in the list for the Local Government Area under study. There are 21, 15 and 22 societies under Ifedapo Ayetoro, Toluwalase and Ifeoluwa CMS respectively. Furthermore, from the selected CTCS, fifteen members each were purposely selected from seven societies, these were based on the fact that the list of members of each society was not available for use and not all members are equally committed to the society. Hence, those present at the society meetings were enumerated for the purpose of the study totaling 104 respondents.

Methods of Data Analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistical analytical techniques were used to analyze the data collected for the study. Descriptive statistics which include percentages and frequency distribution tables were used to analyze the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents. Descriptive statistics was used to identify the sources of loan preferred, their payback period and constraints in obtaining loan.

Model 1: Loan Repayment Model

Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression analytical technique was used to determine the factors affecting

the loan repayment performance of the cooperators. The model in the implicit form is specified as:

$$Q = A_0 + \beta_i X_i + U \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where: Q = Loan Repayment

- A₀ = Constant term of the regression
- β_i = Coefficient of X_i input
- X_i = Independent Variables
- U = Error Term

The explicit form of the model is:

$$Q = b_0 + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 + b_4 X_4 + b_5 X_5 + b_6 X_6 + b_7 X_7 + b_8 X_8 + b_9 X_9 + U \dots (2)$$

Where:

- Q_i = Relative Amount Repaid in Naira
- X₁ = Borrowers' Age in years
- X₂ = Household Size in number of persons
- X₃ = Interest Rate in percentage
- X₄ = Marital Status
- X₅ = Educational Level in years
- X₆ = Credit Size in naira
- X₇ = Year of Credit Experience
- X₈ = Annual Income in naira
- X₉ = Annual Net Income in naira
- U = Error Term

Model 2: Loan Default Model

The Linear Function of multiple regressions was used to estimate the loan default rate of the cooperative members.

$$Y = a_0 + a_1 X_1 + a_2 X_2 + a_3 X_3 + a_4 X_4 + a_5 X_5 + a_6 X_6 + a_7 X_7 + a_8 X_8 + a_9 X_9 + U \dots (2)$$

Y = Loan Default in Naira (₦)

b₀ = Age in years

a₁ – a₈ = Coefficients of explanatory variables (i. e. X₁ – X₈)

X₁ = Age of respondents (years)

X₂ = Gender of respondents (Male = 1, Female = 0)

X₃ = Amount of Loan granted in naira

X₄ = Cooperative size (number)

X₅ = Educational Level in years

X₆ = Household Size (persons)

X₇ = Marital Status

X₈ = Loan duration (Months)

X₉ = Year of Cooperative Experience

U = Error term

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Distribution of Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents

<u>Variables</u>	<u>Frequency</u>	<u>Percentage</u>
	<u>Age (years)</u>	
Less or equal 30	15	14.4
31-40	24	23.1
41-50	30	28.8
51-60	28	26.9
Above 60	7	6.7
<u>Sex</u>		
Male	55	52.9
Female	49	47.1
<u>Marital Status</u>		
Single	13	12.5
Married	75	69.2
Divorced	16	15.4
Widow	3	2.9
<u>Educational Qualification</u>		
Primary	12	11.5
Secondary	39	37.5
National Diploma	14	13.5
Higher National Diploma	22	21.2
Bachelor of Science	17	16.3
<u>Household Size</u>		
1-3	12	11.5
4-6	26	25
7-9	24	23.1
Above 9	16	15.4
<u>Religion</u>		
Christianity	59	56.7
Islam	43	41.3
Traditional	2	1.9
<u>Sources of Loan</u>		
Cooperative society	85	81.7
Micro finance Institution	3	2.9
Universal bank	4	3.8
Daily contribution	12	11.5
<u>Mode of Payback</u>		
Installment	83	79.8
Full	19	20.2
<u>Purpose of Loan</u>		
Business	71	68.3
Estate Acquisition	10	9.6
Household Assets Acquisition	3	2.9
Sponsoring Children Education	11	10.6
Business and Sponsoring Children	7	6.7
Others	2	1.9
<u>Loan Diversion</u>		
None	29	27.9
Purchase of Vehicle	8	7.7
Building of House	12	11.5
Paying of school fees	16	15.4
Marriage	5	4.8
Social Ceremonies	1	1.0
<u>Constraints in obtaining Loan</u>		
None	41	39.4
High interest rate	21	20.2
Inability to produce collateral	10	9.6
Bureaucracy/Protocol	21	20.2
Untimely Disbursement	7	6.7

Others	4	3.8
Total	104	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2012

As presented in Table 1, the age distribution revealed that about 78.8% respondents have their age bracket between 31 – 60 years. This implies that majority of the cooperators are still in their active and productive ages. This support Adeyemo and Akala (1992) findings that Credit institutions might be willing to give loan facility to young and dynamic members who are more likely to adopt new innovation than the older members. The result also revealed that CTCS is dominated by male (52.9%) respondents; this also goes in line with Adeyemo and Akala (1992) discussion that this could be due to the fact that male are said to be more responsible to the welfare of the family than their female counterpart. This implies that majority of the cooperators are married and this indicate that most of them are responsible to the welfare of their household. The importance of education cannot be over emphasized in the adoption of new innovations. Educational attainment of cooperator does not only raise his performance but also increase his ability to understand and evaluate the information on new techniques and processes being disseminated through extension (Olagunju and Adeyemi, 2007). As presented in Table 1, majority of the respondents (89.5%) have educational level beyond primary school indicating that most of them are well knowledgeable, highly educated to enhance their cooperative management performance and accessibility to cooperative loan invariably increase their standard of living and welfare.

The finding shows that respondents with household size between 4-6 are most dominant with the population of 73.1 percent. This translate that the awareness on family planning in this local government area has not been effective and people whose household size is between 4-6 persons are most frequent, probably because they need money to take care of their children welfares.

The finding shows that 81.7 percent of the respondent source for their loan from cooperative society; this is as a result of low interest charges by cooperative society which give members easy means for loan repayment thereby promote their business growth. Majority of the members preferred to pay their loan installmentally than paying in full. Since, 79.8 percent of the members pay installmentally and 20.2 percent pay in full. This indicates that installmental payment is easier

for members than full payment. About 31.7% of the respondents diverted the use of their loan from business purpose to other things which consequently affect negatively their repayment level.

Several problems or obstacles to loan procurement were identified in the study and notable among them are: high interest rate and bureaucracy protocol, inability to produce collateral, untimely disbursement of loan, payback period and mode of payment. Efforts should be made to overcome these constraints so as to enhance the cooperators access to loan for economic expansion and business growth.

Factors affecting Loan Repayment among Cooperators

The result of the regression analysis for the postulated loan repayment is presented in Table 2. Based on the correct signing of the explanatory variables, significance of regression coefficient, the R^2 value and least standard error, the linear form was selected as the best fit for the model. From the Table 2, it could be deduced that the explanatory power of 62.2% of the variations in the loan repayment by the cooperators is explained by the regression and the remaining 37.8% variation is caused by other independent variables which are not included in the model. Thus, the regression had a good fit implying that the most explanatory variables are included in the model. Also, the F-value of 50.155 was significant at 99% level of significance. Thus, it indicates a strong influence of the selected nine variables on the amount repaid.

The coefficient of the variables age, level of education, year of experience and position in the society all statistically significant in relation to loan repayment pattern among the cooperators; this implies that an increase in the unit of these variables will increase the possibility of loan repayment among the cooperators. The coefficient of the household size, interest rate, amount of loan granted and level of income are statistically significant but negative in the loan repayment pattern among the cooperators in the study area; this implies that an increase in the unit of the above-mentioned variables will reduce the chance of loan repayment among the cooperator in the study area.

Table 2: Regression analysis on factors affecting loan repayment among cooperators

Variable Name & Code	Std. Error	Coefficient	T- value
(Constant)	45.685	22250.7	10.308*
Age (X ₁)	0.001	2.998	11.509*
Household Size (X ₂)	0.000	-2.381	-5.981*
Interest Rate (X ₃)	0.022	-2.803	-10.849*
Marital Status (X ₄)	0.001	0.023	-0.524
Education (X ₅)	0.001	0.103	2.454*
Credit Size (X ₆)	0.000	-0.064	-1.624***
Year of experience (X ₇)	0.001	0.501	8.343*
Position in the society (X ₈)	0.002	0.414	9.052*
Annual Income (X ₉)	0.004	0.092	-2.416*

$R = 0.797$; R square = 0.635; Adjusted R square= 0.622; F -value = 50.155*

*=Significant at 1%; **=Significant at 5%; ***=Significant at 10%

Source: Field Survey, 2012

Determinants of Loan Default among Cooperators

Table 3 showed that the co-efficient of the variable age, gender, and cooperative size, level of education, household size, loan duration and year of cooperative experience are significant in the rate of loan default among the cooperators in the study area. This implies that one unit increase in these variables will increase the loan default rate among the cooperators. The co-efficient of the variables, level of education and years of cooperative experience are statistically significant but

negative in the rate of loan default among the cooperators. This implies that an increase in the unit of the above-mentioned variables reduces the loan default rate among the cooperators in the study area. The explanatory power of 41.3% of the variations in the rate of loan default among cooperators is explained by these determinants. Also F -value of 22.011 was significant at 99% level of confidence. Thus, it indicates a moderate influence of the selected nine variables on the rate of loan default.

Table 3: Regression analyses on determinants of loan default among cooperators

Variable Name & Code	Std. Error	Coefficient	T-value
(Constant)	0.587	118.608	12.406
Age (X ₁)	0.074	0.227	3.799*
Gender (X ₂)	0.070	0.292	5.717*
Amount of loan granted (X ₃)	0.053	0.065	1.243
Cooperative Size (X ₄)	0.120	0.132	2.641*
Education (X ₅)	0.078	-0.118	-2.003*
Household Size (X ₆)	0.090	-0.358	5.292*
Marital Status (X ₇)	0.091	-0.098	-1.472
Loan Duration (X ₈)	0.053	0.258	4.242*
Year of Cooperative Experience (X ₉)	0.101	-0.156	-2.530*

$R = 0.658$; R -square = 0.432 Adjusted R -square = 0.413; F -value = 22.011*

*=Significant at 1%; **=Significant at 5%; ***=Significant at 10%

Source; Field Survey 2012

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, this study revealed that age, level of education, year of experience and position in the society are all statistically significant and positive in relation to cooperators' utilization and loan repayment patterns. Despite several constraints to cooperative credit use experienced by some cooperators, the loans provided appear sufficient to meet their farming and business operations which is evident in their increased output, but insufficient for consumption and other pressing needs.

Successful management of credit programme through CTCS for smallholders' farmers who are cooperators depends, to a large extent, on sound knowledge of socio-economic characteristics of the cooperators and their production situation or background. These factors pose three major tasks for the credit administrators namely, how to (i) ensure continuous patronage from farmers; (ii) guide against mis-use of credit; (iii) ensure prompt and full repayment of credit. Patronage can be enlisted through loan education to focus on credit acquisition, utilization and

repayment and removal of unnecessary bureaucracy and harassment associated with credit disbursement and recovery.

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are important to provide the solution to the problem associated to the cooperative society in order to increase their performance in loan repayment. The credit agencies should always endeavour to draw a more convenient disbursement and amortization schedule to conform with economic needs. That is, loan must be adapted to the peculiar needs of the cooperators and repayment condition should be flexible enough to allow for variation and uncertainties in cooperative income. Cooperative society leaders organize seminar for cooperators on how to use the loan in other to yield returns in the investment at end of the business.

REFERENCES

- Adeyemo, R. (1982): "Strategies for Improving Agricultural Credit in Nigeria." *Savings and Development Journal*, VI (1): 85-96.
- Adeyemo, R. and O. Akala. (1992): "Cooperative Fishermen in the Riverine Area of Nigeria." *International Journal of Environmental Management*, 36: 27-34.
- Ayanwale, A.B. and A. S. Bamire. (2000): "Rural Income, Savings And Investment Behaviour among Farmers in Osun State of Nigeria." *The Indian Journal of Economics*, LXXXI(320): 49-60.
- Berthoud, R. and Hinton, T. (1989): *Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society in the United Kingdom*, Policy Studies Institute, Printer Publishers Limited (UK).
- Croteau, J. T. (1956): *The Federal Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society :Policy and Practice*, University of Notre Dame, Harper & Brothers Publishers, New York. Golden Jubilee Brochure Published by CUA Limited
- Ijere MO (1998): "Agricultural Credit and Economic Development. In: Ijere MO, Okorie A (eds) Readings in Agricultural finance Longman Lagos, pp. 4-9.
- Momoh S. and Oso A. O. (1997): Some Determinants of Membership Participation in Credit and Thrift Cooperative Societies in Ogun State, Nigeria. *Journal of Rural Economics and Development*. Vol. 13, No. 2 1998 and 1999. Pp. 95 – 101.
- Openiyi, F.O. (1982): *Saving Investment Behaviour of Farm Household in Ikale and Ilaje/Ese-Odo LGA of Ondo State, Nigeria*. Unpublished B. Agric. Project Report. Pp 11, 35.
- Onyenwaku C.E. and C. M. Ozoh. (1992): "Savings mobilization among rural households in Anambra state of Nigeria." *Quarterly Journal of International Agriculture*, 31(3): 301-309.
- Osuntogun, A. and R. Adeyemo. (1981): "Mobilization of rural savings and credit extension by pre cooperative organizations in Southwest Nigeria." *Savings and Development Journal*, 4: 247-261
- Simanowitz, Anton and Alice Walter (2002): *Ensuring Impact: Reaching the Poorest while Building Financially Self-Sufficient Institutions, and Showing Improvement in the Lives of the Poorest Women and Their Families*. IN Sam Daley-Harris, Ed. Microcredit Summit Campaign. Pathways Out of Poverty. Kumarian: Bloomfield, CT. pp. 101 – 109.

Cite this Article: Akerle EO, Aihonsu JOY, Ambali OI, Oshisanya KP, 2014. Factors Affecting Loan Repayment Performance among Members of Cooperative Thrift and Credit Society in Yewa North Local Government Area, Ogun State, Nigeria. *Greener Journal of Agricultural Sciences*. 4(6):238-244, <http://dx.doi.org/10.15580/GJAS.2014.6.030714135>.